

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Consumers' motivations to purchase green organic foods with special reference to the consumers in Dhaka City

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Abstract

Green organic food is manufactured with environment-friendly technology and has no negative effect on the environment. The aim of this study is to investigate the motivators that influence Bangladeshi consumers' green organic foods purchasing behavior. Data were collected from 100 people using the convenience sampling technique. Questionnaires were employed as research instruments. The Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) for Microsoft Windows version 11 was used to analyze the data. The researcher carried out correlation analysis to investigate the relationship between the variables, as well as regression analysis to evaluate the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable. All of the factors, including peer influence, green advertising, environmental knowledge, and willingness to pay were found to be highly correlated with green purchasing behavior. Regression analysis revealed that environmental knowledge and willingness to pay have a significant role in the suggested model. Peer influence and green advertising have the lowest effect on consumers' green purchasing behavior. The study's implication is that it allows companies to focus more on these motivators that motivate consumers to purchase green organic foods.

Keywords: Green organic food; Motivations; Peer influence; Advertising; Marketing; Bangladesh

1. Introduction

Rapid economic growth and technological advancement make people's lives more convenient, but they also create numerous environmental challenges, including air pollution, water pollution, climate change, and global warming [1]. The sustainability of economic progress, the environment, and society are all directly affected by these issues. Additionally, it has drawn everyone's attention to the environment. Environmentally conscious consumers have increased environmental protection activities and knowledge during the last few decades [1]. Environmental awareness is growing which has a direct impact on how people live their lives and what they value. Many consumers are aware of the value of the environment and the impact that their purchase decisions will have on the ecological environment. Consumers have started changing their habits and purchasing patterns, and they have gradually preferred to buy more environmentally friendly goods [2]. Research interests in how food choices affect health and well-being are growing as a result of public challenges [22, 23, 67].

Green products are intended to reduce or eliminate toxic waste, pollution, and the usage of toxic substances while conserving energy and resources [3]. They may be recyclable, renewable, reusable, and have fewer negative environmental effects than traditional products [4]. Green products not only decrease environmental danger but also develop consumer and societal living standards [1]. Companies are now more aware of the market for green products as a result of consumer demand for environmentally friendly goods. As sustainable development gains popularity, the production of green products has expanded into a vast area of social advancement and economic growth that involves both consumers and businesses. Companies themselves have started to pay attention to environmental issues as an important component of economic development. Since the growth of green businesses contributes to the reduction of

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the expense of excessive waste, the provision of safe and healthy working conditions for employees, and the maintenance of an organization's sustainability and efficiency consequently, businesses are working to create a green economy by coordinating the expansion of environmental protection with the economy. Companies have created a variety of green products to fulfill customer needs in order to expand the market for green products [4, 69]. Companies are looking for solutions to these issues because of the shift in consumer preferences for green products and the requirement for prompt action to reduce environmental challenges. As a result, many businesses have started implementing green production and marketing strategies to satisfy consumers' choices and generate long-term profits [6]. Many customers mention organic food when speaking about foods and health [24]. Organic foods are grown using practices that are both environmentally and socially responsible, such as avoiding using artificial fertilizers or pesticides [25]. In accordance with The U.S. Department of Agriculture (USDA), organic is defined as "a labeling term that indicates that the food or other agricultural product has been produced through approved methods. These methods integrate cultural, biological, and mechanical practices that foster recycling of resources, promote ecological balance, and conserve biodiversity." Organic food is thought to be safer, healthier, and more delicious than traditional food [26, 27, 68].

Although there is a greater demand from consumers for green products and businesses are eager to create green marketplaces, the level of market development for green products is still insufficient. In a previous study, about 30% of customers attempted to incorporate their environmental concerns into their purchasing habits [7]. However, the rate of green product purchases is still relatively low [8]. The growth of the green product industry depends on modifications in consumer purchasing behavior, studying consumer behavior is challenging yet since it takes into account so many different variables. Studying the variables influencing customers' purchase intentions is of utmost importance for businesses as it helps them develop marketing strategies since consumers' green purchasing intentions are a significant expression of consumers' green behavior [1].

The consideration that consumers give to the environment and green products will influence their purchasing choices [9]. Marketers must pay attention to consumer preferences and decision-making processes in order to promote green products [10]. There have been numerous studies on the variables influencing consumers' intentions to make green purchases [11, 12, 13, 15]. A lightweight plastic bottle was the subject of an investigation by Lam et al. [14], who investigated that consumers' purchase intentions were significantly and positively influenced by the product's perceived green value. Additionally, it has been found that green trust influences consumers' intention to buy [16] again, subjective norms of consumers [17, 73]. According to [19], consumer attitudes toward green purchasing can influence their intention to buy and eventually their buying behavior. However, contradicting findings from other studies have been found. In terms of consumption cognition, some researchers believe that green perceived value has little influence on green purchasing intention [18]. Other mentionable finding includes the fact that awareness of the environment did not encourage eco-friendly purchasing [20] and the intention to make green purchases was not significantly influenced by consumer attitudes [21]. There is not enough in-depth review in the literature because of the controversy in findings. The purpose of this study is to determine the variables that affect the consumption behavior of green organic food of the residents of Dhaka city. This study also aims to measure consumer experience, perception, and awareness of green organic foods, as well as the present food consumption scenario.

2. Literature Review

Based on the previous studies, it is found that a variety of elements, including brand name, ecological advertising, environmental packaging, peers, consumer perception of effectiveness, and environmental concerns influence customers' green organic food purchase behavior [28, 29, 30, 72]. The study shows that the following variables have an effect on the purchasing behavior of green organic food.

2.1. Peer Influence

Peer influence is the term used to describe how other people who are viewed as peers affect a person's attitudes, behaviors, and beliefs [32, 33]. Previous research has found that peer influence directly influences on adolescents' green buying behavior [81]. Again, Green involvement and purchasing are significantly influenced by social influence [82]. According to the social learning theory, individuals learn by seeing, imitating, and seeking advice from their peers, and so peers constitute a primary source of knowledge for consumers. Peer network supports green consciousness and behavior, including local environmental involvement and general green purchasing behavior [82]. Thus, customers' purchasing decisions are frequently influenced by coworkers, salesmen, and celebrities [34, 72]. Peer influence, however, can be divided into three categories: utilitarian, value-expressive, and informative [33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38]. Bangladeshi customers are frequently affected by friends, family, salespeople, and celebrities while making green purchases [39]. However, the study proposes the following hypothesis:

- **H₁: Peer influence has a significant and positive effect on green purchasing behavior.**

2.2. Green Advertising

Advertising is defined as the clarity of advertising to imprint consumers' desire to convince and introduce purchasing intention [87]. Green advertising can be perceived as advertising that connects food to the natural environment [88]. One of the most effective ways to reach consumers who are already engaged in environmentally friendly actions is green advertising [41]. Previous research has revealed that green advertising and packaging have a major impact on customer purchasing behavior and can help improve their opinions and improve the likelihood of purchasing green products [42]. Similarly, other researchers believe that green advertising has a major impact on consumer buying intention, which assists customers in making a final purchasing decision [43, 73]. Green advertising, on the other hand, may help consumers who have no prior awareness of any green product to build an understanding of the ecological implications of those products. Consequently, green advertising may increase the interest of customers in green products [44]. However, the study proposes the following hypothesis:

- **H₂: Green advertising has a significant and positive effect on green purchasing behavior.**

2.3. Environmental Knowledge

Environmental knowledge can be defined as a set of concepts, ideologies, facts, and interconnected interactions centered on the environment and ecological elements [45, 46]. Environmental knowledge can also be defined as the thoughts, attitudes, and relationships that individuals know and hold about the environment, as well as the collective tasks that are required to achieve sustainable development [47, 48, 49, 67]. Because of the environmental challenges that have arisen in the modern era, there is a growing public concern [83, 84, 85, 86]. The study of green consumption intentions began with a study of environmental concerns [82]. Previous research has found that environmental knowledge directly influences on adolescents' green buying behavior [81]. Additionally, environmental knowledge is crucial in creating consumer interest in purchasing green products [28]. There is a significant relationship between environmental knowledge and consumer pro-environmental behavior [48]. Previous studies found that environmental knowledge can be categorized as broad or particular [50, 73]. However, the study proposes the following hypothesis:

- **H₃: Environmental knowledge has a significant and positive effect on green purchasing behavior.**

2.4. Willingness to pay

First, the price response model, which gives information for optimal pricing and promotion decisions, is built around consumers' willingness to pay [89]. Second, the price at which new items are introduced must be carefully addressed, since badly chosen prices might imperil development investment and threaten innovation success [90]. Consumers consider price while considering their options for various products and making final buying decisions [56, 57]. Pricing for green foods is thought to be inherently more expensive than for traditional foods [55]. Price is an important consideration in every purchasing choice, especially for young customers [58]. However, several researches revealed that the higher cost is not a significant barrier to purchase green foods [59]. Several researchers found the variable consumers' willingness to pay (WTP) to be empirically significant in their research framework for predicting green buying intention and buyer behavior [53, 54, 71]. Instead, those who care about the environment are willing to pay more for green products as long as the increased cost is justified by other benefits [51, 52]. However, the study proposes the following hypothesis:

- **H₄: Willingness to pay has a significant and positive effect on green purchasing behavior.**

Figure 1 Hypothesized Research Model

3. Material and methods

3.1. Data Collection

To collect primary data, the personal interview technique was used [60]. Data was collected from consumers who are familiar with the term "green organic food" using convenience sampling. The literature was used to establish the standard scales constructs. It is easier to answer an organized questionnaire. As a result, the researcher has made a well-structured questionnaire [50, 51]. Buyer responses were gathered using a five-point Likert scale. Here, 1 said "strongly disagree" and 5 said "strongly agree". The researcher employed 19 statements for performance ratings in the domains of the motives of green organic foods purchasing. The dependent variable, green purchasing behavior, consists of four statements. The statements are included in the appendix. The questionnaire was distributed to a total of 100 respondents. SPSS software was used to conduct the analysis.

3.2. Consumers' Demographic Analysis

Numerical method is used to summarize information from a data set in an ordered manner [73]. There are 53 females and 47 males among the 100 responses. The majority of buyers (52%) are between the ages of 26 and 30, and the majority (53%) are graduates. Here, the majority of buyers of green organic food items are professionals. Only 43% of consumers earn more than 50,000 Bangladeshi taka, while 17 percent earn less than 30,000 taka.

Table 1 Demographic profile of the respondents

		Male	Female	Total
Age	20-25	8 (17.02%)	9 (16.98%)	17 (17%)
	26-30	28 (59.57%)	24 (45.28%)	52 (52%)
	31-35	8 (17.02%)	10 (18.87%)	18 (18%)
	36-40	3 (6.38%)	10 (18.87%)	13 (13%)
		47 (46.93%)	53 (53.07%)	100 (100%)
	Undergraduate	1 (2.13%)	2 (3.77%)	3 (3%)

Education	Graduate	25 (53.19%)	28 (52.83%)	53 (53%)
	Post-graduate	19 (40.43%)	21 (39.62%)	40 (40%)
	Doctorate	2 (4.26%)	2 (3.77%)	4 (4%)
		47 (46.93%)	53 (53.07%)	100 (100%)
Occupation	Student	3 (6.38%)	6 (11.32%)	9 (9%)
	Homemaker	2 (4.26%)	15 (28.30%)	17 (17%)
	Own business	12 (25.53%)	20 (37.74%)	32 (32%)
	Professional	30 (63.83%)	12 (22.64%)	42 (42%)
		47 (47%)	53 (53%)	100 (100%)
Monthly Income	Less than 30,000	5 (10.64%)	12 (22.64%)	17 (17%)
	30,000-50,000	20 (42.55%)	20 (37.74%)	40 (40%)
	More than 50,000	22 (46.81%)	21 (39.62%)	43 (43%)
		47 (47%)	53 (53%)	100 (100%)

4. Results

4.1. Reliability Statistics

Internal reliability test was performed to determine the research instrument's stability and dependability [63]. A reliability statistic (Cronbach's alpha) was used to assess the dependability and internal consistency of each of the 19 attributes examined. The scale has been found to be internally consistent (alpha =.942). This alpha has above the minimum of .70 [74]. According to table 2, the internal reliability for the dependent variable, green purchasing behavior is 0.942.

Table 2 Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.942	19

4.2. Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis is used in marketing research to demonstrate the relationship and strength between two variables. Karl Pearson is a popular correlation coefficient since it explains linear relationships between variables [65]. The greater the number of samples, the more accurate the computation of correlation coefficient. The correlation value should be between +1 and -1, depending on whether the correlation is positive or negative. When the value is +1, the variables are positively related; when the value is -1, the variables are negatively related; and 0 shows that there is no relationship between the variables. Correlation values ranging from .01 to .29 suggest a weak relation, .30 to .49 show a moderate relationship, and .50 to 1.0 indicate a significant relationship between the variables. Bivariate correlation is based on the two-tailed statistical significance level, whereby the highly significant level is $p < .01$ and the significant level is $p < .05$ [61].

Table 3 Correlation Matrix

	PI	GA	EK	WTP	GPB
PI	1				
GA	0.724	1			
EK	0.876	0.754	1		
WTP	0.781	0.670	0.868	1	

GPB	0.840	0.716	0.927	0.870	1
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Note: PI= Peer Influence, GA= Green Advertising, EK= Environmental Knowledge, WTP= Willingness to Pay, GPB= Green Purchasing Behavior.

According to the correlation matrix, there is a considerable relationship between peer influence and green buying behavior. The correlation between peer influence and green purchasing behavior was found to be strong and statistically significant ($r=.840$, $p<.001$). There is a strongly positive relationship between green advertising and green purchasing behavior. The relationship between green advertising and green purchasing behavior was found to be positive and statistically significant ($r=.716$, $p<.001$). The table demonstrates a positive relationship between environmental knowledge and green purchasing behavior. The relationship between environmental knowledge and green purchasing behavior was found to be favorable and statistically significant ($r=.927$, $p<.001$). The relationship between willingness to buy and green purchasing behavior was found to be favorable and statistically significant ($r=.870$, $p<.001$).

4.3. Regression analysis

Regression analysis is used to determine and analyze the relationship between independent and dependent variables [78]. Correlation and regression analysis vary in that correlation reveals the relation between the variables, whereas regression analysis shows the changes in the dependent variables caused by the independent variables [65, 79]. The p-value is calculated to demonstrate the significance of the result. If the p-value is less than .05, the result is at least 95% significant P value less than .01 denotes that the result is significant by at least 99%.

Table 4 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square
1	0.937	0.877	0.872

Table 5 Hypotheses Results

Hypotheses	Relations	B	t	p-value	Results
H ₁	PI → GPB	0.092	1.218	0.226	Not Supported
H ₂	GA → GPB	0.013	0.325	0.746	Not Supported
H ₃	EK → GPB	0.603	6.232	0.000	Supported
H ₄	WTP → GPB	0.241	3.513	0.001	Supported

Note: $p<0.05$; PI= Peer Influence, GA= Green Advertising, EK= Environmental Knowledge, WTP= Willingness to Pay, GPB= Green Purchasing Behavior.

The study intends to look into the impact of peer influence, green advertising, environmental knowledge, and willingness to pay on green purchasing behavior. The dependent variable (green purchasing behavior) was regressed on predictive variables such as peer influence, green advertising, environmental knowledge, and willingness to pay. The R-square value in table 4 is .877, indicating that the independent variables, namely peer influence, green advertising, environmental knowledge, and willingness to pay, cause a 87.7% change in the dependent variable, namely green purchasing behavior.

Furthermore, coefficients were calculated to determine the impact of each factor on the criterion variable (green purchasing behavior). H₁ investigated whether peer influence has a significant and positive effect on green purchasing behavior. The findings demonstrated that peer influence has no effect on green purchasing behavior ($B=.092$, $t=1.218$, and $p=.226$). As a result, H₁ was not supported. H₂ investigated whether green advertising has a significant and positive effect on green purchasing behavior. The findings demonstrated that green advertising has no effect on green purchasing behavior ($B=.013$, $t=.325$, and $p=.746$). As a result, H₂ was not supported. H₃ investigated whether environmental knowledge has a significant and positive effect on green purchasing behavior. The findings demonstrated that environmental knowledge has a significantly positive effect on green purchasing behavior ($B=.603$, $t=6.232$, and $p=.000$). As a result, H₃ has contributed to the model. H₄ investigated whether willingness to pay has a significant and positive effect on green purchasing behavior. The findings demonstrated that willingness to pay has a significantly positive effect on green purchasing behavior ($B=.241$, $t=3.513$, and $p=.001$). So, H₄ was supported.

5. Discussion

The hypotheses established and evaluated in this study explained the impact of motivations (peer influence, green advertising, environmental knowledge, willingness to pay) on the purchase behavior of green organic foods. Data were collected from the residents of Dhaka city. The study revealed a strong positive relationship among the variables. Four hypotheses were proposed to investigate the relationships between the independent variables (peer influence, green advertising, environmental knowledge, and willingness to pay) and the dependent variable (green purchasing behavior). It was found that environmental knowledge and willingness to pay have a substantial influence on green organic foods consumers' purchasing intentions in Dhaka city of Bangladesh. Therefore, the third hypothesis H₃ and fourth H₄ have been accepted. Peer influence and green advertising have no significant influence on green organic foods consumers' purchasing intentions. So, the first hypothesis H₁ and the second hypothesis H₂ have not been accepted. Producers and sellers of green organic foods should implement these motivating aspects to ensure high levels of customer satisfaction. These findings will help green organic foods marketers persuade green organic foods buyers and therefore grow sales satisfactorily.

6. Conclusion

Although many consumers are still unfamiliar with the term "green organic foods", expanding marketing tactics will help this industry. If marketers prioritize the reasons people buy green organic foods, it will cause a revolution in the food industry, as sales are increasing rapidly. The four motivations for purchasing green organic foods are peer influence, green advertising, environmental knowledge, and willingness to pay. Environmental knowledge and willingness to pay are important contributors to this study as a result, companies must develop a green concept in green organic foods and focus on environmental knowledge and willingness to pay however, peer influence, and green advertising are not. As a result, there is a greater opportunity to do additional research on the factors that influence customers' perceptions of buying green organic foods in Dhaka city of Bangladesh.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest with the publication of the manuscript or an institution or product that is mentioned in the manuscript.

Statement of ethical approval

The present research work does not contain any studies performed on animals/humans subjects by the author.

Statement of informed consent

The study involves information about the participants and informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

- [1] Zhuang W, Luo X, Riaz MU. On the factors influencing green purchase intention: A meta-analysis approach. *Frontiers in Psychology*. 2021 Apr 9;12:644020.
- [2] Soon T, Kong W. The influence of consumer's perception of green products on green purchase intention (Doctoral dissertation, Universiti Malaysia Sabah).
- [3] Ottman JA, Stafford ER, Hartman CL. Avoiding green marketing myopia: Ways to improve consumer appeal for environmentally preferable products. *Environment: science and policy for sustainable development*. 2006 Jun 1;48(5):22-36.

- [4] Dangelico RM, Pontrandolfo P. From green product definitions and classifications to the Green Option Matrix. *Journal of cleaner production*. 2010 Nov 1;18(16-17):1608-28.
- [5] Dangelico RM, Pujari D. Mainstreaming green product innovation: Why and how companies integrate environmental sustainability. *Journal of business ethics*. 2010 Sep;95:471-86.
- [6] Dangelico RM, Vocalelli D. "Green Marketing": An analysis of definitions, strategy steps, and tools through a systematic review of the literature. *Journal of Cleaner production*. 2017 Nov 1;165:1263-79.
- [7] Young W, Hwang K, McDonald S, Oates CJ. Sustainable consumption: green consumer behaviour when purchasing products. *Sustainable development*. 2010 Jan;18(1):20-31.
- [8] Rex E, Baumann H. Beyond ecolabels: what green marketing can learn from conventional marketing. *Journal of cleaner production*. 2007 Jan 1;15(6):567-76.
- [9] de Moura AP, Cunha LM, Castro-Cunha M, Lima RC. A comparative evaluation of women's perceptions and importance of sustainability in fish consumption: An exploratory study among light consumers with different education levels. *Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal*. 2012 Jun 8;23(4):451-61.
- [10] Cherrier H, Black IR, Lee M. Intentional non-consumption for sustainability: Consumer resistance and/or anti-consumption?. *European Journal of Marketing*. 2011 Nov 15;45(11/12):1757-67.
- [11] Gil MT, Jacob J. The relationship between green perceived quality and green purchase intention: A three-path mediation approach using green satisfaction and green trust. *International Journal of Business Innovation and Research*. 2018;15(3):301-19.
- [12] Hashim M, Baig SA, Abrar M, Afzal A, Mohsin M. Effects of Green Marketing on Green Purchase Intentions. *Dialogue (1819-6462)*. 2019 Apr 1;14(2).
- [13] Sun Y, Wang S. Understanding consumers' intentions to purchase green products in the social media marketing context. *Asia pacific journal of marketing and logistics*. 2020 Apr 21;32(4):860-78.
- [14] Lam AY, Lau MM, Cheung R. Modelling the relationship among green perceived value, green trust, satisfaction, and repurchase intention of green products. *Contemporary Management Research*. 2016 Mar 22;12(1).
- [15] Wang J, Tao J, Chu M. Behind the label: Chinese consumers' trust in food certification and the effect of perceived quality on purchase intention. *Food Control*. 2020 Feb 1;108:106825.
- [16] Konuk FA, Rahman SU, Salo J. Antecedents of green behavioral intentions: a cross-country study of Turkey, Finland and Pakistan. *International journal of consumer studies*. 2015 Nov;39(6):586-96.
- [17] Bong Ko S, Jin B. Predictors of purchase intention toward green apparel products: A cross-cultural investigation in the USA and China. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management: An International Journal*. 2017 Mar 13;21(1):70-87.
- [18] Juliana J, Djakasaputra A, Pramono R. Green perceived risk, green viral communication, green perceived value against green purchase intention through green satisfaction. *Journal of Industrial Engineering & Management Research*. 2020 Aug 10;1(2):124-39.
- [19] Sreen N, Purbey S, Sadarangani P. Impact of culture, behavior and gender on green purchase intention. *Journal of retailing and consumer services*. 2018 Mar 1;41:177-89.
- [20] Jaiswal D, Kant R. Green purchasing behaviour: A conceptual framework and empirical investigation of Indian consumers. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*. 2018 Mar 1;41:60-9.
- [21] Xu X, Hua Y, Wang S, Xu G. Determinants of consumer's intention to purchase authentic green furniture. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*. 2020 May 1;156:104721.
- [22] Block LG, Grier SA, Childers TL, Davis B, Ebert JE, Kumanyika S, Laczniak RN, Machin JE, Motley CM, Peracchio L, Pettigrew S. From nutrients to nurturance: A conceptual introduction to food well-being. *Journal of Public Policy & Marketing*. 2011 Apr;30(1):5-13.
- [23] Bublitz MG, Peracchio LA, Andreasen AR, Kees J, Kidwell B, Miller EG, Motley CM, Peter PC, Rajagopal P, Scott ML, Vallen B. Promoting positive change: Advancing the food well-being paradigm. *Journal of Business Research*. 2013 Aug 1;66(8):1211-8.
- [24] Ares G, de Saldamando L, Giménez A, Claret A, Cunha LM, Guerrero L, de Moura AP, Oliveira DC, Symoneaux R, Deliza R. Consumers' associations with wellbeing in a food-related context: A cross-cultural study. *Food Quality and preference*. 2015 Mar 1;40:304-15.

- [25] Shafie FA, Rennie D. Consumer perceptions towards organic food. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*. 2012 Jan 1;49:360-7.
- [26] Magnusson MK, Arvola A, Hursti UK, Åberg L, Sjöden PO. Attitudes towards organic foods among Swedish consumers. *British food journal*. 2001 Apr 1;103(3):209-27.
- [27] Magkos F, Arvaniti F, Zampelas A. Organic food: buying more safety or just peace of mind? A critical review of the literature. *Critical reviews in food science and nutrition*. 2006 Jan 1;46(1):23-56.
- [28] Mostafa MM. Antecedents of Egyptian consumers' green purchase intentions: A hierarchical multivariate regression model. *Journal of international consumer marketing*. 2006 Oct 25;19(2):97-126.
- [29] Kim Y, Choi SM. Antecedents of green purchase behavior: An examination of collectivism, environmental concern, and PCE. *ACR North American Advances*. 2005.
- [30] Kumar B, Manrai AK, Manrai LA. Purchasing behaviour for environmentally sustainable products: A conceptual framework and empirical study. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*. 2017 Jan 1;34:1-9.
- [31] Ansar N. Impact of green marketing on consumer purchase intention. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*. 2013 Oct 2;4(11):650.
- [32] Ahmad N, Yousuf M, Shabeer K, Imran M. A comprehensive model on consumer's purchase intention towards counterfeit mobiles in Pakistan. *Journal of Applied Science Research*. 2014;4(5):131-40.
- [33] Makgosa R, Mohube K. Peer influence on young adults' products purchase decisions.
- [34] Maram HK, Kongsompong K. The power of social influence: East-West comparison on purchasing behavior.
- [35] Bearden WO, Etzel MJ. Reference group influence on product and brand purchase decisions. *Journal of consumer research*. 1982 Sep 1;9(2):183-94.
- [36] Childers TL, Rao AR. The influence of familial and peer-based reference groups on consumer decisions. *Journal of consumer research*. 1992 Sep 1;19(2):198-211.
- [37] Lessig VP, Park CW. Promotional perspectives of reference group influence: Advertising implications. *Journal of advertising*. 1978 Jun 1;7(2):41-7.
- [38] John SF, Christopher JA. Influence of peer in purchase decision making of two-wheelers: a study conducted in Coimbatore. *European Journal of Commerce and Management Research (EJCMR) Research (EJCMR)*. 2013;2(1):1-5.
- [39] Hafez M. Factors Affecting Green Purchase Behavior of Bangladeshi Customers: A Study on Energy Saving Lamp. *Journal of Science and Technology*. 2017;6(1):17-29.
- [40] Rahman MS, Hossain MI, Hossain GM. Factors affecting environmental knowledge and green purchase behavior of energy saving light users in Bangladesh: An empirical study. *International Journal of Academic Research in Economics and Management Sciences*. 2019;8(3):364-84.
- [41] Davis JJ. Consumer response to corporate environmental advertising. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*. 1994 Jun 1;11(2):25-37.
- [42] D'Souza C, Taghian M, Lamb P, Peretiatkos R. Green products and corporate strategy: an empirical investigation. *Society and business review*. 2006 May 1;1(2):144-57.
- [43] Barber N. "Green" wine packaging: targeting environmental consumers. *International Journal of Wine Business Research*. 2010 Nov 9;22(4):423-44.
- [44] Dagher GK, Itani O. Factors influencing green purchasing behaviour: Empirical evidence from the Lebanese consumers. *Journal of Consumer Behaviour*. 2014 May;13(3):188-95.
- [45] Fryxell GE, Lo CW. The influence of environmental knowledge and values on managerial behaviours on behalf of the environment: An empirical examination of managers in China. *Journal of business ethics*. 2003 Aug;46:45-69.
- [46] Conraud-Koellner E, Rivas-Tovar LA. Study of green behavior with a focus on Mexican individuals.
- [47] Sawant R. A study on awareness and demand pattern amongst consumers WRT green products. *International Journal of Marketing and Technology*. 2015;5(1):136-48.
- [48] Rokicka E. Attitudes toward natural environment: A study of local community dwellers. *International Journal of Sociology*. 2002 Sep 1;32(3):78-90.

- [49] Chan RY, Lau LB. Antecedents of green purchases: a survey in China. *Journal of consumer marketing*. 2000 Jul 1;17(4):338-57.
- [50] Polonsky MJ, Vocino A, Grau SL, Garma R, Ferdous AS. The impact of general and carbon-related environmental knowledge on attitudes and behaviour of US consumers. *Journal of Marketing Management*. 2012 Mar 1;28(3-4):238-63.
- [51] Olson EL. It's not easy being green: the effects of attribute tradeoffs on green product preference and choice. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*. 2013 Mar;41:171-84.
- [52] Thøgersen J, Jørgensen AK, Sandager S. Consumer decision making regarding a “green” everyday product. *Psychology & Marketing*. 2012 Apr;29(4):187-97.
- [53] Grankvist G, Biel A. The importance of beliefs and purchase criteria in the choice of eco-labeled food products. *Journal of environmental psychology*. 2001 Dec 1;21(4):405-10.
- [54] Benedetto G, Rugani B, Vázquez-Rowe I. Rebound effects due to economic choices when assessing the environmental sustainability of wine. *Food policy*. 2014 Dec 1;49:167-73.
- [55] Vega-Zamora M, Torres-Ruiz FJ, Murgado-Armenteros EM, Parras-Rosa M. Organic as a heuristic cue: What Spanish consumers mean by organic foods. *Psychology & Marketing*. 2014 May;31(5):349-59.
- [56] De Medeiros JF, Ribeiro JL, Cortimiglia MN. Influence of perceived value on purchasing decisions of green products in Brazil. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 2016 Jan 1;110:158-69.
- [57] Moser AK. Thinking green, buying green? Drivers of pro-environmental purchasing behavior. *Journal of consumer marketing*. 2015 May 11;32(3):167-75.
- [58] Chaudhary R. Green buying behavior in India: an empirical analysis. *Journal of Global Responsibility*. 2018 Jun 1;9(2):179-92.
- [59] Chaudhary R, Bisai S. Factors influencing green purchase behavior of millennials in India. *Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal*. 2018 Jul 5;29(5):798-812.
- [60] Khatun A, Roy SK. Do green marketing strategies influence green buying intentions? Evidence from developing economy. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*. 2022;7(10):766-77.
- [61] Roy SK, Ahmed J. A relational study of communication, reputation and cooperation on relationship satisfaction in the context of apparel sector in Bangladesh. *British Open Journal of Business Administration*. 2016;1:1-0.
- [62] Roy SK, Chowdhury SH, Islam S, Siddique S. Socio-economic status of the street garment vendors: A descriptive study in the context of Dhaka city, Bangladesh. *Asian Journal of Sustainable Business Research*. 2021;2(2):95-117.
- [63] Malhotra Y. Why knowledge management systems fail: enablers and constraints of knowledge management in human enterprises. *Handbook on knowledge management 1: Knowledge matters*. 2004:577-99.
- [64] Malhotra NK, Dash SJ. An applied orientation. *Marketing Research*. 2010;2.
- [65] Malholtra NK. *Marketing Research: an Applied Orientation Sixth Edition* Pearson Education.
- [66] Chowdhury SH, Roy SK, Arafin M, Siddique S. Green HR practices and its impact on employee work satisfaction- a case study on IBBL, Bangladesh. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science, Delhi*. 2019;3(3):129-38.
- [67] Chowdhury S, Roy S. Evaluating the impact of insurance companies in the development of insurance practices in Bangladesh. *Scholar Journal of Business and Social Science*. 2015;1(1):37-42.
- [68] Islam S, Hossain MS, Roy SK. Performance evaluation using CAMELS model: A comparative study on private commercial banks in Bangladesh. *International Journal for Asian Contemporary Research*. 2021;1(4):170-6.
- [69] Khatun A, Roy SK. Do green marketing strategies influence green buying intentions? Evidence from developing economy. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*. 2022;7(10):766-77.
- [70] Siyal S, Ahmed MJ, Ahmad R, Khan BS, Xin C. Factors influencing green purchase intention: Moderating role of green brand knowledge. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 2021 Oct 14;18(20):10762.
- [71] Roy SK. E-learning Portal Success in higher education organizations: A multi-group comparison. *Journal of Social, Humanity, and Education*. 2023 May 5;3(3):197-218.

- [72] Roy SK. Green Factors and Green Behavioral Intentions: A Hybrid Two-Stage Modeling Approach. Available at SSRN 4462203.
- [73] Roy SK. Green Initiatives and Environmental Sustainability: The Moderating Role of Environmental Values. Available at SSRN 4454040.
- [74] Roy SK. Impact of SMS advertising on purchase intention for young consumers. *International Journal of Financial, Accounting, and Management*. 2023 Mar 8;4(4):427-47.
- [75] Roy SK. Influencing factors for pursuing agriculture as a career for agriculture undergraduates: a two-stage approach. *Entrepreneurship Education*. 2023 Jun 4:1-35.
- [76] Roy SK. YouTube's influential factors for academic achievement: A two-stage approach. *Telematics and Informatics Reports*. 2023 Jun 1;10:100060.
- [77] Roy SK, Ahmed J. A relational study of communication, reputation and cooperation on relationship satisfaction in the context of apparel sector in Bangladesh. *British Open Journal of Business Administration*. 2016;1:1-0.
- [78] Roy SK, Chowdhury SH, Islam S, Siddique S. Socio-economic status of the street garment vendors: A descriptive study in the context of Dhaka city, Bangladesh. *Asian Journal of Sustainable Business Research*. 2021;2(2):95-117.
- [79] Roy SK, Islam S. Influence of confidence factors on e-learning acceptance for future use by university students: evidence from an emerging economy. *SN Social Sciences*. 2023 Sep 7;3(9):160.
- [80] Kaufmann HR, Panni MF, Orphanidou Y. Factors affecting consumers' green purchasing behavior: An integrated conceptual framework. *Amfiteatru Economic Journal*. 2012;14(31):50-69.
- [81] Lee K. Opportunities for green marketing: young consumers. *Marketing intelligence & planning*. 2008 Sep 19;26(6):573-86.
- [82] Nagarajan M, Saha R, Kumar R, Sathasivam D. Impact of peer influence and environmental knowledge on green consumption: Moderated by price premium. *International Journal of Social Ecology and Sustainable Development (IJSESD)*. 2022 Nov 1;13(6):1-6.
- [83] Abdelzaher D, Newburry W. Do green policies build green reputations?. *Journal of Global Responsibility*. 2016 Sep 12;7(2):226-46.
- [84] Binder M, Blankenberg AK. Green lifestyles and subjective well-being: More about self-image than actual behavior?. *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*. 2017 May 1;137:304-23.
- [85] Sihvonen S, Partanen J. Implementing environmental considerations within product development practices: a survey on employees' perspectives. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 2016 Jul 1;125:189-203.
- [86] Tang CM, Lam D. The role of extraversion and agreeableness traits on Gen Y's attitudes and willingness to pay for green hotels. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*. 2017 Jan 9;29(1):607-23.
- [87] Chan JC, Jiang Z, Tan BC. Understanding online interruption-based advertising: Impacts of exposure timing, advertising intent, and brand image. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*. 2009 Dec 22;57(3):365-79.
- [88] Schmuck D, Matthes J, Naderer B. Misleading consumers with green advertising? An affect–reason–involvement account of greenwashing effects in environmental advertising. *Journal of Advertising*. 2018 Apr 3;47(2):127-45.
- [89] Lea E, Worsley T. Australians' organic food beliefs, demographics and values. *British food journal*. 2005 Dec 1;107(11):855-69.
- [90] Qing TC, Jusoh ZM. Factor Influencing Consumer Willingness to Pay for Green Foods Consumption.

Appendix

Constructs	Items and Statements	Sources
Peer Influence	PI1: My friends often discuss the environmental issues related to green organic food with me. PI2: My friends, often, recommend green organic food to me. PI3: My friends often share their experiences and knowledge about green organic foods with me.	(Khare, 2015)

Green Adverstising	<p>GA1: I believe that green advertising is a good source of information about green organic foods.</p> <p>I know that green advertising is good at addressing environmental problems.</p> <p>GA3: Because of the green advertising of green organic foods I believe they are safer to eat.</p> <p>GA4: I have more confidence in advertised green products than in unadvertised green ones.</p> <p>GA5: I think green advertising presents a true picture of the product being advertised.</p>	(Haytko & Matulich, 2008)
Environmental Knowledge	<p>EK1: I know more about environmental issues than the average person.</p> <p>EK2: I know the reasons to select green organic foods which helps to protect the environment.</p> <p>EK3: I understand the environmental phrases and symbols on the package of green organic foods.</p> <p>EK4: I know that buying green organic foods is environmentally safe.</p>	(Mostafa, 2006)
Willingness to Pay	<p>WTP1: I would pay more for a green product that is making efforts to be environmentally sustainable.</p> <p>WTP2: I would be willing to pay this extra percentage on the green products to support the organization's/ product efforts to be environmentally sustainable.</p> <p>WTP3: I feel proud to have environment- friendly products in my house even though they are more costly than conventional ones.</p>	(Kang et al. 2012 & Jang et al. 2011)
Green Purchaseing Behavior	<p>GPB1: I prefer green organic foods over non-green products when their product qualities are similar.</p> <p>GPB2: I buy green organic foods because they are environmentally-friendly.</p> <p>GPB3: I buy green organic foods even if they are more expensive than the nongreen ones.</p> <p>GPB4: When I want to buy a green organic food, I look at the ingredient label to see if it contains environmentally damaging things.</p>	(Lee, 2008)